

THE VARIATION OF CATIONIC ACTIVITY IN COLLOIDAL CLAYS WITH CONCENTRATION OF THE DISPERSE PHASE

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The variations of the activity of Na^+ , K^+ and Ca^{2+} ions of clays, saturated with these ions, have been determined at various concentrations of the clays by means of clay-membrane electrodes. The ionic activities increase almost linearly up to a certain concentration of the clay (11%, 10% and 5% for Na-, K- and Ca- clays respectively) but afterwards the rate of increase slows down. The percentage dissociation of Na- and K- clays decreases sharply at first, followed by an increase, and a more or less flattened maximum at about 10-11%. Ca-clay, however, shows no initial decrease in dissociation which rises to a fairly sharp maximum at about 1.2% clay concentration.

The clay-membrane electrodes for the determination of cationic activities were developed by Marshall ("Colloid Chemistry of Silicate Minerals", Academic Press, 1949). Later on Marshall *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) and Marshall and Chatterjee (*J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1950, 52, 671) used the membrane electrodes to study the variation of metal-ion activities in course of neutralisation of acid colloidal clays with hydroxides and oxides of Na, K, NH_4 , Ca, Mg and Ba. Mitra (D. Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1954) using a number of Indian clays prepared clay-membrane electrodes suitable for measurement of ionic activities over a wide range, and reported measurement of Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} ion activities with the help of the membrane electrodes. Cationic activity measurements, reported above, generally refer to dilute suspensions, and the results are often applied directly to investigate ion-exchange characteristics of clay, present in soil. The clay, present in soil, is more or less gel-like and hardly assumes a sol state under the natural conditions. Hence, there may be little justification in extrapolating information available in dilute solutions to concentrated pastes.

The present enquiry aims at an understanding of the variation, if any, of Na^+ , K^+ and Ca^{2+} ion activities of clays with the concentrations of the latter.

EXPERIMENTAL

The clay-membrane electrodes used in this investigation were prepared according to the method of Mitra (*loc. cit.*) by the usual process of evaporating clay suspensions in 20 thin films and heating them to desired temperatures. The standardisation and performance of clay membranes as electrodes were thoroughly studied in this laboratory (Mitra, *loc. cit.*). The clay membranes, fixed to one end of a pyrex tubing, separated the base-saturated clay suspension or paste and a solution of known ionic activity (of say, NaCl, KCl or CaCl_2). The potential difference across the membrane between two tiny calomel electrodes was measured with the help of a Cambridge potentiometer. The ionic activity was calculated from E.M.F. of the following cell, according to the Nernst relation,

$$E = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a(\text{solution})}{a(\text{clay})}$$

$\text{Hg}, \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{Na (K/or Ca) Cl} \mid \text{Membrane} \mid \text{Na (K or Ca) clay}, \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{Hg}$.

The variation of cationic activity with concentration of the clay was studied in the following manner. The clay was first concentrated by slow evaporation to a pasty mass. The solid content was determined by oven-drying a known weight of the paste. The diluted suspensions were then obtained from the pastes by adding known amounts of water, which was allowed to equilibrate for 96 hours.

The results of a_{Na} , a_K and a_{Ca} determinations are shown graphically in Figs. 1 and 2 and recorded in Tables I-III.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

DISCUSSION

The nature of variation of activity of Na^+ and K^+ ions in the respective clays with the concentration of the latter is more or less the same. There are, however, two points of difference. Firstly, the initial slope is slightly higher for Na-clay, and secondly, the curve is much less steep after an almost linear relation up to 10% in the case of K-clay and little above 11% in the case of Na-clay. It is probable that the more hydrated Na^+ ion prevents, at least partially, overlapping of the double layer, as the sol becomes concentrated so that the activity of Na^+ ions is not lowered to that extent which occurs in K-clay.

The effect of ion hydration becomes more evident in the Ca-clay, particularly when it is compared with Na- and K- clays. The initial slope equals that of Na-clay, but the rise in the activity of Ca^{2+} ion is prevented at a much lower (nearly 5%) concentration of the clay when as a result of relatively small hydration of Ca^{2+} ions, overlapping of the double layer is more likely.

Overlapping of the double layer is likely to result either in the increase in activity or in an 'immobilisation' of the ions. According to the latter process, those ions, which were registering their activity in dilute suspensions, become 'immobilised', so to say, with the result that the rate of increase in ionic activity due to the increase in concentration of the clay diminishes.

TABLE I
Known Na^+ -ion activity = 0.0263.

No.	Clay/suspension (g./100 g.).	Total molal Na^+ conc. in clay (c).	E. M. F.	Na^+ -activity of clay (a).	%Dissociation (a/c × 100).
1	16.978	0.1401	-10 mV	0.02735	19
2	11.944	0.0985	1.6	0.02472	25
3	10.389	0.0857	3.4	0.02291	29
4	4.725	0.0389	28.9	0.00851	22
5	3.174	0.0262	38.5	0.00575	22
6	2.389	0.0197	42.4	0.00501	25
7	1.889	0.0156	47.4	0.00417	27
8	1.683	0.0139	48.0	0.00407	29
9	1.378	0.0114	51.4	0.00355	31
10	0.482	0.0040	74.9	0.00132	33

TABLE II
Known K⁺-ion activity = 0.027.

No.	Clay/suspension (g./100 g.).	Total molal conc. of K^+ in clay (c).	E. M. F.	K^+ activity of clay (a).	%Dissociation (a/c × 100).
1	16.960	0.1392	7.8 mV	0.01992	14
2	9.955	0.0821	12.4	0.01665	20
3	7.344	0.0604	19.4	0.01263	21
4	4.034	0.0333	35.8	0.00663	20
5	3.676	0.0303	28.4	0.00605	20
	3.376	0.0278	41.3	0.00539	19
7	3.122	0.0257	42.7	0.00515	20
8	2.756	0.0227	45.6	0.00459	20
	2.074	0.0171	56.1	0.00303	16
	1.387	0.0114	65.6	0.00210	18
10	0.834	0.0070	77.9	0.00129	19
11	0.418	0.0035	95.5	0.00078	23

TABLE III

Known Ca^{2+} -ion activity = 0.0001.

No.	Clay/suspension (g./100 g.).	Total molal conc. of Ca^{2+} in clay (c).	E. M. F.	Ca^{2+} activity of clay (a) $\times 10^5$.	% Dissociation ($a/c \times 100$).
1	6.088	0.0251	10.3 mV	4.48	0.18
2	3.143	0.0130	15.8	2.92	0.38
3	2.123	0.0088	20.0	2.70	0.24
4	1.289	0.0053	24.8	1.44	0.27
5	0.278	0.0012	46.1	0.27	0.24

Tables I, II and III record in the last column of each the percentage dissociation of the ion, calculated from the observed activity (a) and known concentration (c) of the ion present in the base-saturated clay. The percentage dissociation first decreases very sharply with concentration, but shows an increase at a higher concentration of the clay and continues to do so followed by a fairly sharp fall. The increase is shown by Na-clay at about 4-5%, and the same for K-clay is 2-3%; the sharp fall almost coincides with the flattening of the activity curve. The graphs shown in figures represent the behaviour of Ca-clay which, unlike Na- and K-clay, shows no initial decrease of dissociation. On the other hand, the %dissociation reaches a maximum, followed by a sharp fall, as in the case of Na- and K-clays. The fall is observed at about 1.2% clay, whereas the concentration at which Ca^{2+} ion activity shows a decrease is higher.

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